

The impact of software metrics in NASA metric data program dataset modules for software defect prediction

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses software metrics and their impact on software defect prediction values in the NASA metric data program (MDP) dataset. The NASA MDP dataset consists of four categories of software metrics: halstead, McCabe, LoC, and misc. However, there is no study showing which metrics participate in increasing the area under the curve (AUC) value of the NASA MDP dataset. This study utilizes 12 modules from the NASA MDP dataset, where these 12 modules are being tested into 14 relationships of software metrics derived from the four existing metric categories. Subsequently, classification is performed using the k-nearest neighbor (kNN) method. The research concludes that software metrics have a significant impact on the AUC value, with the LoC+McCabe+misc metrics relationship influencing the improvement of the AUC value. However, the metrics relationship that has the most impact on achieving less optimal AUC values is McCabe. Halstead metric also plays a role in decreasing the performance of other metrics.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past two decades, there has been a rapid increase in the demand for software development in all sectors [1]. Along with this, the quality of the software becomes extremely important, particularly where software defects are concerned [2]. A software defect is generally defined as a deviation from the specifications or requirements that should be possessed by software, this defect can cause the software to fail the functions that are typically reported during the software testing phase [3], [4]. In 2018, it was reported that the identification and refinement of software defects and losses due to software failures in production accounted for 50% of the total cost of software development [5]. It has also been reported that a minor error in data conversion caused a \$125 million NASA spacecraft to disappear in space [6]. All of these reports have made research into software defects and software defect prediction (SDP) one of the most extensive in recent years. SDP itself is a classification process performed to detect code or modules of software that are likely to fail or have defects. This process is implemented using previously available defect data [7].

Since the beginning of 2000, SDP studies have widely used data from the NASA repository. This repository is known as NASA metric data program (MDP). NASA MDP become popular among researchers because its original format is easy to use in research of SDP, moreover, the difficulty of obtaining software defect data has made public repositories of software defect data very popular [8], [9]. The NASA MDP

dataset consists of 12 pre-cleaned module datasets, and every dataset module represents a system/subsystem of NASA's software [10], [11]. Each module in the NASA MDP dataset contains a set of static software metrics which used to determine the presence of defects in the software module [12], [13]. Software metrics themselves are widely used in SDP studies and have a crucial role in the construction of SDP models as one of the indicators for the measurement of software quality and the estimation of the presence of defects and vulnerabilities in a code [14], [15]. Some studies that use software metrics already conducted include [16]–[21].

In research using software metrics as indicators, it is important to have an understanding of software metrics. The understanding of metrics relies on the concepts of the metric itself as well as its relations to other metrics, each metrics relationship will have an impact on each other [21]. Several research studying the relationships between metrics have already been conducted, such as a comparison between static metrics and dynamic weighted metrics performed by [22], the analysis of metrics on object-oriented system (OOS) to evaluate and identify the relationship between metrics value with software security performed by [23] and study about the relationship between two types of metrics, namely object-oriented metrics with procedural-oriented metrics performed by [24]. Although research on the metrics relationship has been widely conducted, most studies do not provide clear evidence on how a metric can influence other metrics, or which metrics have the most significant impact on the relationships between them. Moreover, it is not known whether all existing metric attributes are relevant in SDP.

Based on the explanation above, this research will study the influence of software metrics on the accuracy of SDP in the k-nearest neighbor (kNN) classification method. kNN is chosen to be the classification method because it is one of the methods widely used in various studies of SDP, as conducted by [25]–[29]. There will be 14 relationships of software metrics used in this research.

2. METHOD

2.1. Collecting data

The dataset utilized in this study originates from the NASA repository known as the NASA MDP. This particular dataset was selected due to its widespread use in software metrics research and its explicit design for research in this area [30]. NASA MDP provides two versions of a clean dataset, namely D' (which includes duplicate and inconsistent instances) and D'' (which excludes duplicate and inconsistent instances). The NASA MDP dataset version used in this study is D'' which is taken from (<https://github.com/klainfo/NASADefectDataset>). The amount of data for each dataset is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. NASA MDP D'' datasets [11]

Dataset	Attributes	Modules	Defective	Non-defective	Defective (%)
CM1	38	327	42	285	12.8
JM1	22	7,720	1,612	6,108	20.8
KC1	22	1,162	294	868	25.3
KC2	40	194	36	158	18.5
MC1	39	1,952	36	1,916	1.8
MC2	40	124	44	80	35.4
MW1	38	250	25	225	10
PC1	38	679	55	624	8.1
PC2	37	722	16	706	2.2
PC3	38	1,053	130	923	12.3
PC4	38	1,270	176	1,094	13.8
PC5	39	1,694	458	1,236	27.0

2.2. Software metrics

Certain studies suggest that SDP models formulated based on software metrics are effective in predicting defects in source code [30]. The datasets module in NASA MDP is formed by 4 software metric categories, namely LoC, halstead, McCabe, and misc [31]. In Table 2 it shows 4 software metric categories with features in each category.

2.3. Preprocessing data

Data preprocessing techniques are often employed to minimize the interference of raw data, including noisy data, and transform it into a form that is more understandable [32], [33]. During the preprocessing stage, pivotal procedures encompass feature selection, and sampling methods [34]. Feature selection is one of the steps in data preprocessing where relevant features are selected in the learning model [35]. In this research, preprocessing data is conducted by performing feature selection based on 4 software metrics categories

available in NASA MDP dataset modules. These 4 software metrics categories are paired into the following pairs which are shown in Table 3.

Table 2. Software metrics in NASA MDP [31]

Metrics category	Features	Number of features
LoC	CYCLOMATIC_COMPLEXITY	6
	CYCLOMATIC_DENSITY	
	DESIGN_COMPLEXITY	
	ESSENTIAL_COMPLEXITY	
Misc	BRANCH_COUNT	17
	CALL_PAIRS	
	CONDITION_COUNT	
	DECISION_COUNT	
	DECISION_DENSITY	
	DESIGN_DENSITY	
	EDGE_COUNT	
	ESSENTIAL_DENSITY	
	PARAMETER_COUNT	
	GLOBAL_DATA_COMPLEXITY	
	GLOBAL_DATA_DENSITY	
	MAINTENANCE_SEVERITY	
	MODIFIED_CONDITION_COUNT	
	MULTIPLE_CONDITION_COUNT	
NODE_COUNT		
NORMAL_CYLOMATIC_COMPLEXITY		
PERCENT_COMMENTS		
McCabe	LOC_BLANK	6
	LOC_CODE_AND_COMMENT	
	LOC_COMMENTS	
	LOC_EXECUTABLE	
	NUMBER_OF_LINES	
Halstead	LOC_TOTAL	12
	HALSTEAD_CONTENT	
	HALSTEAD_DIFFICULTY	
	HALSTEAD_EFFORT	
	HALSTEAD_ERROR_EST	
	HALSTEAD_PROG_TIME	
	HALSTEAD_VOLUME	
	NUM_OPERANDS	
	NUM_OPERATORS	
	NUM_UNIQUE_OPERANDS	
	NUM_UNIQUE_OPERATORS	
	HALSTEAD_LENGTH	
	HALSTEAD_LEVEL	

Table 3. Metrics pairs used in the study

Metric quantity	Metrics pairs
1 metric	Halstead
	LoC
	McCabe
	Misc
2 metrics	Halstead+LoC
	Halstead+McCabe
	Halstead+Misc
	LoC+McCabe
	LoC+Misc
	McCabe+Misc
3 metrics	LoC+McCabe+Misc
	Halstead+McCabe+Misc
	Halstead+LoC+Misc
	Halstead+LoC+McCabe

2.4. Classification

KNN is a classification method based on supervised learning [36]. The fundamental concept of kNN is to classify training data into specific classes through majority voting based on the k value, the k value itself is a constant value defined by the user, and the class that represents most of the training data will be assigned

to the test pattern [37], [38]. In this study, the k values used are $k=3$, $k=5$, $k=7$, $k=9$, $k=11$, $k=13$, and $k=15$. Before classification with kNN is performed, the dataset is divided into training data and testing data using 10-fold cross-validation.

2.5. Evaluation

To evaluate the results obtained in this study, we will compare the area under the curve (AUC) values for each metric relationship within the same dataset module with those of other metric relationships. The highest AUC value for each k value in a metric relationship will be selected and then compared to the highest value held by other metric relationships. The AUC values will also be compared with AUC values from the dataset modules containing all metrics.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The classification method used in this study is limited to kNN along with the NASA MDP dataset from the NASA repository, consisting of 12 dataset modules. The testing process is performed on each dataset module, both on the original dataset and on the relationships between each category of software metrics within the NASA MDP dataset. On each dataset module, testing is carried out with several values of k , namely $k=3$, $k=5$, $k=7$, $k=9$, $k=11$, $k=13$, and $k=15$. This testing phase is conducted to determine the most optimal AUC value for each module dataset and to understand the impact of the relationships between metrics.

As seen in the testing results in Table 4 (in Appendix), each pair of metrics for each dataset module has an impact on the AUC value of a dataset. Some metric pairs influence increasing the AUC value. However, some metric pairs result in values that are not better than the AUC value of the dataset composed of all metric categories. The highest value for each dataset module is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Comparison of highest value in each metrics relationship

In Figures 1 and 2, the horizontal color line shows each dataset value (where the value is shown in the vertical axis) for the metrics relationship (where the value is shown in the horizontal axis). In Figure 1 it shows that the relationships among metrics have a significant impact on the difference in AUC values. The metric relationship that has the most significant role in increasing the AUC value is the relationship between LoC+McCabe+misc. This metric relationship provides the best AUC value in the module datasets JM1, KC3, MC2, PC4, and PC5. Meanwhile, in module datasets PC1, PC2, and PC3, the highest AUC values are obtained in the LoC+McCabe metric relationship. In the CM1 module dataset, the highest AUC value is associated with the LoC metric. The KC1 module dataset achieves the highest AUC value in the halstead+LoC+McCabe metric relationship, and the MC2 module dataset obtains the highest AUC value in the McCabe+misc metric relationship. Meanwhile, in Figure 2 it is shown that the McCabe metric has been found to play a role in producing less optimal AUC values, as evidenced by the AUC values in the CM1, KC1, KC3, MC2, and PC3 module datasets. On the other hand, the halstead metric plays a role in decreasing the performance of other metrics.

Figure 2. Comparison of lowest value in each metrics relationship

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the test results, it can be concluded that the relationship for each software metric in the NASA MDP dataset significantly affects the classification AUC value. Furthermore, the choice of the k value in the kNN classification method also affects the AUC value in each software metrics relationship. The software metrics relationship that has the most impact on achieving a high AUC value is the relationship between the LoC+McCabe+misc metric categories, however, the metrics relationship that has the most impact on achieving less optimal AUC values is McCabe. The halstead metric also plays a role in decreasing the performance of other metrics.

APPENDIX

Table 4. Testing result

Dat aset	x	All Metri cs	Halste ad	LoC	McCa be	Misc	Halste ad + LoC	Halste ad + McCa be	Halste ad + Misc	LoC + McCa be	LoC + Misc	McCa be + Misc	LoC + McCa be + Misc	Halste ad + McCa be + Misc	Halste ad + LoC + Misc	Halste ad + LoC + McCa be
CM	3	0.56	0.56	0.676	0.498	0.505	0.558	0.56	0.559	0.672	0.676	0.518	0.656	0.559	0.56	0.558
	5	0.605	0.605	0.695	0.482	0.568	0.604	0.605	0.606	0.693	0.691	0.542	0.685	0.606	0.606	0.604
	7	0.62	0.616	0.72	0.484	0.57	0.616	0.616	0.617	0.724	0.697	0.561	0.697	0.617	0.62	0.616
	9	0.617	0.614	0.726	0.516	0.587	0.616	0.614	0.616	0.719	0.711	0.583	0.708	0.616	0.617	0.616
	11	0.634	0.633	0.723	0.524	0.588	0.633	0.633	0.633	0.711	0.692	0.603	0.69	0.633	0.634	0.633
	13	0.668	0.664	0.73	0.494	0.595	0.666	0.664	0.667	0.735	0.7	0.617	0.697	0.667	0.669	0.666
	15	0.657	0.651	0.739	0.514	0.607	0.652	0.651	0.654	0.738	0.71	0.612	0.709	0.654	0.657	0.652
JM	3	0.574	0.574	0.596	0.51	0.507	0.573	0.572	0.573	0.628	0.616	0.511	0.629	0.574	0.574	0.573
	5	0.591	0.59	0.615	0.53	0.526	0.591	0.588	0.589	0.648	0.633	0.533	0.652	0.59	0.591	0.591
	7	0.603	0.602	0.628	0.548	0.544	0.604	0.603	0.604	0.659	0.646	0.55	0.664	0.604	0.604	0.604
	9	0.61	0.607	0.639	0.558	0.556	0.611	0.607	0.607	0.666	0.653	0.558	0.669	0.607	0.611	0.611
	11	0.618	0.615	0.647	0.566	0.568	0.618	0.615	0.616	0.672	0.66	0.569	0.671	0.615	0.619	0.618
	13	0.624	0.621	0.647	0.574	0.569	0.624	0.622	0.622	0.672	0.665	0.575	0.676	0.622	0.624	0.624
	15	0.629	0.625	0.65	0.581	0.572	0.628	0.652	0.625	0.676	0.67	0.58	0.679	0.625	0.629	0.628
KC	3	0.524	0.525	0.547	0.533	0.525	0.528	0.52	0.519	0.543	0.582	0.533	0.56	0.526	0.543	0.668
	5	0.587	0.591	0.591	0.57	0.551	0.597	0.593	0.59	0.608	0.621	0.575	0.614	0.595	0.59	0.598
	7	0.617	0.618	0.602	0.621	0.598	0.617	0.619	0.619	0.623	0.63	0.619	0.634	0.622	0.616	0.617
	9	0.628	0.625	0.611	0.617	0.621	0.626	0.626	0.624	0.632	0.637	0.61	0.635	0.627	0.628	0.628
	11	0.639	0.642	0.609	0.623	0.612	0.639	0.641	0.641	0.634	0.634	0.616	0.634	0.641	0.639	0.64
	13	0.651	0.649	0.621	0.624	0.616	0.65	0.649	0.649	0.636	0.637	0.619	0.645	0.65	0.65	0.649
	15	0.652	0.647	0.617	0.616	0.609	0.652	0.648	0.648	0.636	0.646	0.612	0.642	0.648	0.652	0.652
KC	3	0.439	0.468	0.49	0.391	0.574	0.452	0.48	0.471	0.469	0.464	0.544	0.455	0.513	0.483	0.439
	5	0.515	0.497	0.554	0.552	0.604	0.54	0.504	0.537	0.524	0.55	0.612	0.572	0.499	0.532	0.55
	7	0.579	0.571	0.648	0.639	0.705	0.575	0.594	0.578	0.658	0.656	0.674	0.671	0.59	0.591	0.587
	9	0.585	0.591	0.668	0.647	0.687	0.598	0.589	0.586	0.669	0.692	0.691	0.702	0.606	0.583	0.604
	11	0.618	0.62	0.705	0.663	0.694	0.61	0.626	0.614	0.66	0.732	0.7	0.719	0.615	0.616	0.613
	13	0.637	0.641	0.691	0.663	0.713	0.641	0.643	0.638	0.648	0.718	0.717	0.703	0.645	0.637	0.641
	15	0.645	0.645	0.676	0.671	0.699	0.642	0.641	0.644	0.655	0.748	0.72	0.748	0.639	0.642	0.644

Table 4. Testing result (*Continue*)

Dat aset	k	All Metri cs	Halst ead	LoC	McC abe	Misc	Halst ead + LoC	Halst ead + McCa be	Halst ead + Misc	LoC + McCa be	LoC + Misc	McCa be + Misc	LoC + McCa be + Misc	Halst ead + McCa be + Misc	Halst ead + LoC + Misc	Halst ead + LoC + McCa be
MC 1	3	0.671	0.628	0.778	0.613	0.723	0.661	0.638	0.651	0.779	0.795	0.723	0.796	0.651	0.671	0.661
	5	0.681	0.632	0.769	0.667	0.796	0.673	0.634	0.67	0.779	0.815	0.782	0.804	0.67	0.681	0.672
	7	0.701	0.653	0.768	0.696	0.803	0.682	0.655	0.699	0.773	0.806	0.81	0.806	0.699	0.701	0.682
	9	0.709	0.66	0.759	0.681	0.825	0.689	0.672	0.706	0.764	0.8	0.823	0.8	0.706	0.709	0.689
	11	0.728	0.689	0.752	0.695	0.823	0.706	0.701	0.726	0.758	0.792	0.826	0.792	0.726	0.728	0.706
	13	0.733	0.703	0.755	0.691	0.838	0.709	0.706	0.73	0.766	0.786	0.825	0.787	0.731	0.733	0.709
15	0.745	0.712	0.759	0.722	0.842	0.719	0.716	0.743	0.766	0.781	0.828	0.791	0.743	0.745	0.719	
MC 2	3	0.628	0.625	0.674	0.647	0.681	0.624	0.625	0.627	0.669	0.715	0.67	0.717	0.627	0.628	0.624
	5	0.631	0.629	0.684	0.624	0.711	0.629	0.629	0.629	0.686	0.717	0.714	0.702	0.629	0.631	0.629
	7	0.62	0.62	0.642	0.607	0.654	0.62	0.62	0.62	0.661	0.724	0.666	0.735	0.62	0.62	0.62
	9	0.616	0.616	0.668	0.591	0.676	0.616	0.616	0.616	0.674	0.717	0.659	0.714	0.616	0.616	0.616
	11	0.635	0.635	0.642	0.612	0.689	0.635	0.635	0.635	0.646	0.722	0.693	0.728	0.635	0.635	0.635
	13	0.618	0.618	0.654	0.644	0.662	0.618	0.618	0.618	0.656	0.701	0.653	0.696	0.618	0.618	0.618
M W1	3	0.512	0.508	0.575	0.66	0.66	0.508	0.508	0.512	0.583	0.635	0.648	0.628	0.512	0.512	0.508
	5	0.523	0.522	0.639	0.632	0.681	0.522	0.522	0.526	0.709	0.698	0.682	0.691	0.526	0.523	0.522
	7	0.56	0.539	0.678	0.694	0.671	0.539	0.539	0.559	0.693	0.704	0.671	0.702	0.559	0.56	0.539
	9	0.598	0.598	0.676	0.671	0.703	0.599	0.598	0.598	0.687	0.688	0.709	0.684	0.598	0.598	0.599
	11	0.589	0.589	0.678	0.671	0.721	0.589	0.589	0.589	0.675	0.695	0.733	0.697	0.589	0.589	0.589
	13	0.599	0.596	0.677	0.667	0.723	0.596	0.596	0.599	0.677	0.701	0.74	0.703	0.599	0.599	0.596
15	0.6	0.6	0.661	0.682	0.732	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.668	0.714	0.736	0.71	0.6	0.6	0.6	
PC1	3	0.507	0.507	0.71	0.63	0.662	0.508	0.507	0.508	0.713	0.723	0.672	0.707	0.508	0.507	0.508
	5	0.519	0.525	0.755	0.637	0.689	0.524	0.525	0.519	0.768	0.783	0.703	0.789	0.519	0.519	0.524
	7	0.533	0.534	0.785	0.645	0.703	0.534	0.533	0.533	0.791	0.816	0.716	0.822	0.533	0.533	0.534
	9	0.554	0.551	0.8	0.671	0.73	0.553	0.551	0.552	0.791	0.821	0.717	0.821	0.551	0.554	0.553
	11	0.566	0.568	0.804	0.653	0.72	0.566	0.568	0.567	0.819	0.814	0.727	0.814	0.567	0.566	0.566
	13	0.572	0.571	0.812	0.642	0.701	0.573	0.571	0.571	0.818	0.826	0.708	0.822	0.571	0.572	0.573
15	0.591	0.591	0.806	0.637	0.699	0.592	0.591	0.591	0.816	0.849	0.695	0.847	0.591	0.591	0.592	
PC2	3	0.519	0.519	0.72	0.466	0.473	0.52	0.519	0.519	0.703	0.523	0.471	0.499	0.519	0.519	0.52
	5	0.507	0.507	0.729	0.47	0.476	0.507	0.507	0.507	0.714	0.509	0.451	0.512	0.507	0.507	0.507
	7	0.517	0.517	0.728	0.519	0.523	0.517	0.517	0.517	0.747	0.55	0.522	0.568	0.517	0.517	0.517
	9	0.508	0.508	0.724	0.5	0.509	0.508	0.508	0.508	0.745	0.579	0.525	0.582	0.508	0.508	0.508
	11	0.494	0.494	0.719	0.482	0.56	0.494	0.494	0.494	0.752	0.66	0.515	0.673	0.494	0.494	0.494
	13	0.592	0.592	0.77	0.464	0.597	0.592	0.592	0.591	0.792	0.681	0.574	0.684	0.591	0.592	0.592
15	0.642	0.643	0.787	0.474	0.614	0.642	0.643	0.641	0.792	0.679	0.637	0.677	0.641	0.642	0.642	
PC3	3	0.613	0.609	0.681	0.566	0.654	0.614	0.608	0.613	0.708	0.661	0.65	0.665	0.613	0.613	0.615
	5	0.658	0.655	0.719	0.585	0.682	0.654	0.75	0.657	0.739	0.697	0.693	0.706	0.657	0.658	0.654
	7	0.666	0.665	0.741	0.607	0.689	0.665	0.665	0.661	0.764	0.715	0.704	0.721	0.661	0.666	0.665
	9	0.676	0.671	0.744	0.621	0.719	0.671	0.671	0.674	0.769	0.732	0.728	0.741	0.674	0.676	0.671
	11	0.674	0.667	0.746	0.651	0.721	0.673	0.667	0.673	0.763	0.733	0.738	0.746	0.673	0.674	0.673
	13	0.671	0.663	0.748	0.666	0.725	0.668	0.665	0.666	0.758	0.75	0.732	0.762	0.666	0.671	0.668
15	0.667	0.666	0.751	0.666	0.739	0.665	0.666	0.667	0.759	0.764	0.738	0.768	0.667	0.667	0.665	
PC4	3	0.592	0.565	0.775	0.635	0.725	0.567	0.564	0.584	0.809	0.817	0.732	0.813	0.584	0.592	0.568
	5	0.592	0.568	0.806	0.689	0.774	0.574	0.567	0.588	0.829	0.829	0.771	0.838	0.588	0.592	0.575
	7	0.606	0.574	0.824	0.715	0.782	0.579	0.577	0.598	0.843	0.852	0.797	0.852	0.598	0.604	0.579
	9	0.602	0.58	0.828	0.709	0.807	0.579	0.58	0.601	0.836	0.854	0.813	0.852	0.601	0.603	0.579
	11	0.607	0.588	0.827	0.708	0.81	0.583	0.588	0.609	0.838	0.856	0.816	0.858	0.609	0.607	0.583
	13	0.611	0.592	0.826	0.707	0.816	0.591	0.592	0.611	0.839	0.857	0.819	0.859	0.611	0.611	0.591
15	0.619	0.6	0.826	0.706	0.821	0.602	0.6	0.615	0.84	0.857	0.823	0.857	0.615	0.619	0.602	
PC5	3	0.57	0.571	0.623	0.603	0.631	0.577	0.571	0.57	0.639	0.647	0.652	0.654	0.573	0.576	0.577
	5	0.641	0.642	0.665	0.669	0.702	0.646	0.638	0.631	0.68	0.704	0.694	0.692	0.636	0.633	0.643
	7	0.654	0.654	0.693	0.692	0.7	0.654	0.65	0.654	0.704	0.723	0.715	0.712	0.655	0.654	0.65
	9	0.671	0.667	0.704	0.7	0.706	0.668	0.665	0.671	0.717	0.732	0.717	0.732	0.67	0.67	0.668
	11	0.679	0.677	0.707	0.718	0.711	0.679	0.676	0.679	0.719	0.729	0.714	0.73	0.678	0.68	0.679
	13	0.685	0.683	0.709	0.723	0.711	0.684	0.683	0.685	0.721	0.731	0.723	0.733	0.684	0.685	0.685
15	0.688	0.685	0.715	0.729	0.712	0.687	0.684	0.684	0.723	0.736	0.723	0.737	0.685	0.688	0.687	

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